

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D5.2 – “Initial Communication and Dissemination Master Plan”

Work Package 5 – Dissemination and Exploitation

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

EC	European Commission
ES	Energy Storage
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RTO	Research and Technology organisation
WG(s)	Working Group(s)
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The StoRIES project aims at facilitating and accelerating the energy transition, in particular in the field of new materials for energy storage and hybrid energy storage solutions. The main technological objectives of StoRIES are linked to the energy storage development by providing access to world-class research infrastructures and services, with a focus on improving materials for devices and optimizing hybrid energy systems with a view to make energy technologies more competitive and reducing costs. In addition, StoRIES focuses on the analysis of socio-technical and environmental aspects of new developments and systems and provides training and education on these issues.

D5.2 First Draft communication and dissemination plan introduces the StoRIES Project Dissemination and Communication objectives and its implementation plan to be used by the consortium to ensure the high visibility, accessibility and promotion of the project and its results during the 4-year project period. The goal is also to create a solid foundation for the efficient exploitation of the project results after the end of the project. The document will be a reference framework for evaluating the impact of communication and dissemination activities and will be updated and adjusted as the project progresses.

To ensure maximal impact of dissemination and communication activities, StoRIES will focus on communicating the potential of the Storage Research Infrastructure Eco-System to a clearly defined target audience.

The specific activities detailed in the communication plan will address the general public to raise awareness on the project and its achievements. The communication activities will also target key stakeholders that have a relevant role in fields and activities that are undertaken by the project. The communication and dissemination plan has been structured in a way that should be easily readable and offer easy access to methods and tools that can be used for both internal and external communication. Various sections cover a wide area of activities ranging from dissemination objectives, identification of stakeholders, KPIs, methods, role assignment etc. In summary, this document presents:

- Dissemination objectives and targeted audience
- Communication tools and activities
- Design profiles, graphic and textual material
- An unambiguous list with events and responsibilities
- An annex with extensive lists and examples of dissemination material.

The document will rely heavily on and influence other deliverables and is considered a living document. The objective is to accommodate for expected and mandatory use of human resources and communication material given also unexpected events.

INTRODUCTION

This document describes the communication and dissemination plan of StoRIES that will be used during the four years of the project. It provides the guidelines for the communication and dissemination activities of the StoRIES project. Chapter 1 focuses on this plans' goals, objectives, and targets; Chapter 2 on the communications tools, channels, and means used; Chapter 3 on content coordination; Chapter 4 on the indicators selected to analyse the communication's results; and Chapter 5 on the partners' roles and responsibilities. Finally, the appendices can be found at the end of the document.

StoRIES project aims at initiating a long-term, coordinated research effort among leading private companies, universities and research institutions with expertise in the domain of Energy Storage (ES) technologies to identify and promote ways to scale up technologies within the EU. In addition, StoRIES focuses on the analysis of socio-technical and environmental aspects of new developments and systems and provides training and education on these issues.

The communication and dissemination strategy has been designed to target a wide range of stakeholders spanning from policy makers, public bodies, technology providers, Transmission System Operators (TSO) and Distribution System Operators (DSO), energy suppliers, European industries, scientific communities, energy communities and cooperatives, consumers as well as the general public.

This document has been elaborated by CLERENS, which is the leader of Work Package 5, dedicated to Communication and Dissemination Activities. Under CLERENS' guidance, each consortium partner, as well as the linked-third parties will bring into the project their experience and contact network, guaranteeing a range of diversified connections of stakeholders. The dissemination will ensure the publicity of the goals achieved and will establish a public knowledge allowing stakeholders to get a clear understanding of the challenges of the current energy management systems in building and the potential for innovative solutions to increase energy efficiency.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will play a key role for the StoRIES project: in the four years, new information will be collected, and the results and feedback will be used to improve future Horizon 2020 projects.

1 GOALS, OBJECTIVES AND AUDIENCE

1.1 Communication and dissemination long-term goals

The main goal of all communication activities within the StoRIES project is to spread the idea and raise public awareness about the development and needs for cost-effective, environmentally friendly, and socially acceptable Energy Storage (ES) systems through the hybridisation of storage technologies.

It is also targeted to increase the economic impact of innovation actions undertaken within the project by speeding the adoption of developed technologies/products/services, through market and non-market-channels, towards new customers, countries, regions, sectors, markets and organisations. It also aims to push for new solutions, which will benefit target end-users/adopters.

1.2 Communication and dissemination objectives

StoRIES has three key objectives related to communication and dissemination as a whole:

1. Creating visibility and raise awareness among relevant stakeholders about the project concept and expected outcomes
2. Disseminating the projects' results to show the benefits that the StoRIES system architecture can provide to users/adopters through participation in workshops and conferences at the European and international level
3. Promoting final project's outcomes and engaging stakeholders in the replication possibilities, focusing on the promotion of the complete project results which will stimulate replications of the concept and enlargements to other potential applications.

1.3 Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy and activities follow principles and best practices successfully tested by CLERENS and in line with the EC graphical guidelines for successful dissemination. The focal point of the StoRIES overall dissemination strategy is the identification and mapping of targeted stakeholders (**whom to disseminate to**) and understanding of their needs and characteristics so as to tailor clear and concise messages (**what to disseminate**) to the different target audiences. This also comes to ensure the use of the most appropriate and efficient dissemination channels and communication tools and drive the development of proper material per target stakeholders (**how to disseminate**). It further defines a time plan (**when to disseminate**) with specific objectives and target focuses per phase in the lifetime of the project, assisting all project partners in implementing communication activities and reaching the dissemination and exploitation objectives throughout the project implementation. Focusing at reaching a wider audience beyond the main targeted stakeholders of the project, the Communication and Dissemination Plan will outline liaison and networking activities with other EU funded and national projects, initiatives and networks that will further enhance the dissemination range and impact.

1.4 Targeted audience and communication channels

A list of audiences and targets, formulated on the basis of a preliminary analysis conducted during the proposal phase, has been elaborated.

Indeed, it is a key step in the communication and dissemination process to identify groups of stakeholders, in order to design the most appropriate courses of action to engage these actors. Given the presence of a variety of stakeholders, tailor-made strategies are required. Differentiating and

tailoring the message is the key to achieve sound communication. Predictably, the differentiation strategies adopted will change as time passes, as they will be finetuned and improved.

CLERENS, with the support of StoRIES partners, has identified a list of potential targeted audience. It is useful to do further analysis to better understand their relevance and the perspective they offer and to understand their relationship to the issues and each other.

A first investigation has found four relevant groups of targeted audience. This framework could be reviewed throughout the project.

1.4.1 Policymakers and Public Bodies (EU, national, regional and municipal)

A key for effective dissemination of the results is to reach policy makers and public bodies. European Commission and European Parliament, regional local authorities, permitting bodies and municipalities will be targeted in order to influence the future of ES technologies providing multiple services.

Important events such as the European Sustainable Energy Week are key objectives for the dissemination strategy of the project. The messages to be sent focus on the potential of StoRIES' technologies to be deployed on the market, lesson learned and results from the project.

1.4.2 Technology providers, TSO/DSO and energy suppliers

Technology providers, as well as TSO/DSOs and energy suppliers (who can exploit the developed technologies) and relevant players of the energy system will be involved. The project focuses on the optimisation of hybrid ES systems to provide multiples services, so the whole range of energy system stakeholders is targeted as relevant audience to disseminate project results.

1.4.3 European industry and scientific community

StoRIES will act in different research fields, including new and improved materials and the optimisation of hybrid energy systems. StoRIES involves a relevant number of industry-oriented Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and it expects to provide wide new knowledge to the scientific community, mostly in the field of energy storage systems, ES and their impact assessment. This audience will be addressed by on technology performance/improvement, and key findings.

1.4.4 Energy communities, energy cooperatives, consumers and general public

Energy communities, energy cooperatives, consumers and general public are also important targets as a part of the Dissemination Plan. Public acceptance is the key for the deployment of ES systems solutions; a proper dissemination of the project is thus needed to reach citizen organisations and general public.

The following table highlights the just mentioned target groups, provides a brief explanation, and suggests the communication channels to be used.

Table 1 Targeted audience and communication channels

Target Groups	Communication channels/tools	Goals	Message
Policymakers and Public Bodies: DG ENER, ITRE	-Final Conference, National/International conferences	-Influence policy priorities/raise awareness	“StoRIES’ technologies need to receive support as they will benefit the European

committee, Batteries Europe, Joint Research Centre, etc.	-International scientific/technical publications -Liaison with relevant EU communities -Website, social media	-Use StoRIES results for future policy making and project funding -Show that StoRIES provides innovative ES technologies fostering the cooperation in the ES sector	ES community and the market"
Technology providers, TSO/DSO and energy suppliers: ENTSO-E, Terna, EnBW, Plan Energy	-Workshops, seminars -Education sessions -Collaboration with relevant projects -Dissemination material	-Mobilise sector's interest -Foster cooperation -Improve knowledge and know-how -Raise awareness -Disseminate project results	"StoRIES provides multiple services through the optimization of hybrid ES systems for the whole range of ES stakeholders that can benefit from them"
European industry and scientific community: ETIP SNET, Batteries Europe, BRIDGE, EASE, EERA, EUA, EUREC, EARTO, IEA, etc.	-International scientific/technical publications -Workshops, seminars, presentations at conferences, symposia -Education and training sessions -Collaboration with relevant projects	-Mobilise sector's interest -Foster cooperation -Improve knowledge and know-how -Raise awareness -Disseminate project results	"Investing in StoRIES technologies and solutions is beneficial for their industry- oriented RTOs and will provide new knowledge to the scientific community"
Energy communities, energy cooperatives, consumers and general public: BEUC, Rescoop, VZBV	- Website, social media -Events organised and/or participated by the project members -Dissemination material - Promotional video - Press releases and Articles	-Raise awareness on technology and innovation - Raise awareness on role of citizen in energy storage - Raise awareness on role of public funding	"StoRIES solutions will benefit the general public, fostering its involvement in the energy storage field"

The following table presents similar projects with whom StoRIES project could partner with for different types of collaborations and initiatives.

Table 2 Similar H2020 projects which StoRIES has identified and could partner with the organisation of events

Project Acronym	Project Title	Grant agreement	Duration	Topic	Connection with StoRIES
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Battery2030PLUS (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957213)	BATTERY 2030+ large-scale research initiative: At the heart of a connected green society	957213	1 Sept 2020 31 Aug 2023	LC-BAT-15-2020 - Coordinate and support the large-scale research initiative on Future Battery Technologies	Enables long-lasting European leadership in markets such as road transport and stationary energy storage
ERIGRID 2.0 (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870620)	European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition	870620	1 Apr 2020 30 Sept 2024	INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 - Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities	Addresses the challenges of the energy transition by widening and advancing access to European research infrastructure
PANTERA (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824389)	PAN European Technology Energy Research Approach	824389	1 Jan 2019 31 Dec 2022	LC-SC3-ES-7-2018 - Pan-European Forum for R&I on Smart Grids, Flexibility and Local Energy Networks	Bridges the gaps in research and innovation in the energy field that exist between EU Member States
RI-URBANS (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036245)	Research Infrastructures Services Reinforcing Air Quality Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial Areas	101036245	1 Oct 2021 30 Sept 2025	LC-GD-9-1-2020 - European Research Infrastructures capacities and services to address European Green Deal challenges	Demonstrates how advanced service tools from atmospheric research infrastructures (RI) can be adapted to tackle air quality challenges and societal needs in urban and industrial areas.

PAUL (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101037319)	Pilot Applications in Urban Landscapes - Towards integrated city observatories for greenhouse gases (ICOS Cities)	101037319	1 Oct 2021 31 Dec 2025	LC-GD-9-1-2020 - European Research Infrastructures capacities and services to address European Green Deal challenges	Provides a unique data sets feeding diverse models and scientific studies, while testing the feasibility of modelling approaches in various areas
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The dissemination of StoRIES activities through presentations at external events, such as conferences and exhibitions, will play a significant role in the project as it will mainly target the relevant actors in the industry. The external events will be an opportunity to present the project, thanks to the support of the dissemination material and the preparation of a targeted project presentation.

Several recurring conferences and events have been identified, in which the project’s aims and achievements can be presented:

Table 3 Public and private events (including online) where StoRIES could involve or be presented by Consortium partners

Event	Date	Location	Activities performed	Partners involved	People reached
5th International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies	5-7-Sep-2022	Eindhoven, Netherlands	Policy Conference	TBD	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public
European Sustainable Energy Week	26-30-Sept-2022	Online and in person (TBC)	Policy Conference	TBD	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public
World Energy Storage Conference	12-14 Oct 2022	Birmingham, UK	Conference	TBC	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public
Energy Storage Global Conference	11-13 Oct 2022	Brussels, Belgium	Policy Conference	EASE	Policymakers, industry, scientific community,

					general public
Enlit Europe	29-Nov-1-Dec-2022 (TBC)	Frankfurt, Germany	Forum	TBD	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public
Energy Infrastructure Forum 2022	Nov-2022 (TBC)	Copenhagen, Denmark	Forum	TBD	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public
EES 2023	13-16 June 2023	Munich, Germany	Conference	TBD	Policymakers, industry, scientific community, general public

2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND TOOLS

The communication and dissemination tools and actions used for StoRIES are complementary and mutually reinforcing. As highlighted in the previous chapter, several audiences will be targeted differently. CLERENS and its partners will combine, among others, events, networking, and media relations to achieve a multifaceted communication and dissemination strategy.

2.1 Visual Identity

2.1.1 Logo, templates

The visual aspect of the project has received particular attention. A common public image / branding for the project allows an easier identification by the public and ensures better visibility and immediate recognition. The logo displayed below has been selected by Consortium partners after an internal brainstorming and consultation.

Figure 1 Logo of StoRIES

2.1.2 List of communication and dissemination materials

The communication and dissemination materials where the logo and project identity will be used are the following (non-exhaustive list):

- Project website
- Social media
- All documents developed within the framework of the project and in particular the documents to be submitted to the European Commission such as deliverables, agendas, minutes of meetings, etc.
- PowerPoint presentations used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by consortium partners
- Dissemination materials such as leaflets, presentation template, brochures, roll-ups, etc.
- Physical and online events organised or participated in by the project.

A specific template for the project deliverables, presentations as well as for the official documentation and other dissemination activities is defined in order to maintain coherence among the partners in their interaction with the public. Also, in this case, an established and well organised format allows the

public to recognize the project immediately. The common formats have been developed starting from the project logo and the colours selected for the project.

In particular, in order to facilitate document preparation, CLERENS has prepared:

- Text template (Word);
- Meeting minutes template (Word);
- Presentation template (PPT);
- Deliverable template (Word).

These documents will be delivered by e-mail and uploaded to the private project repository. They are also present in Appendix A of this document.

2.1.3 Use of EU logo, emblem and acknowledgement

As stated in Article 29.4 of the General Agreement (GA), every piece of dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem; when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Furthermore, any dissemination of results must include the acknowledgement of EU funding through the following texts:

- For communications activities: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036910."
- For patents: "The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036910."
- For standardisation activities: "Results incorporated in this standard received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036910".
- For infrastructure, equipment and major results: "This [infrastructure][equipment][result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036910."

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036910

Figure 2 EU Emblem with text

(The logo is available in Appendix B)

2.2 Website and digital marketing

2.2.1 Website

The StoRIES website will be the core communication and dissemination channel of the project. It is an instrument that can achieve great visibility for the project and it allows to share knowledge easily and with few barriers. Due to its flexibility, it will be the reference point for many target audiences. The website will rely on an easy-to-use design; the platform will be intuitive and user-friendly also for users using mobile phones. Also, the website has the same colour palette of the logo, in order to achieve consistency.

www.storiesproject.eu

The website gives public access to relevant non-IP-sensitive results. It will provide an overview of the project, detailed information about its objectives, news and event announcements, as well as public deliverables and analysis. Some areas of the website will be more prominent in order to highlight certain aspects of the project. Similarly, particular attention will be dedicated to the dissemination of StoRIES results.

The “Forum” section offers a collaborative area to the users of the website and the eco-system. After signing up, the members can begin a conversation thread, as well as add texts, pictures, videos, and open debates. To maintain a safe environment for the website readers and members, the comments and posts shared will be monitored by moderators from CLERENS.

Below, figure 3 shows a map of the website, with all content pages, both parent and child ones.

Figure 3: StoRIES website map

The website was created by CLERENS in collaboration with the coordinating team of the project from KIT. It was created on M5 (March) and will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project. These updates present news related to the project’s advancements, as well as articles and publications. Social media buttons will be integrated in the website, to promote the project through different platforms. This way, a wider dissemination to both technical and non-technical audiences will be possible.

CLERENS will regularly monitor the website visits (every 6 months) and evaluated. Google Analytics will also be used, an instrument that provides statistics about the website’s traffic showing in-depth data.

This will allow to better understand the behaviour of the user population, and adapt the communication strategy accordingly.

Images related to the website can be found on Appendix C.

2.2.2 StoRIES on social media

StoRIES will rely on social media to spread news about the project and its activities. However, social network will not be used just to share information: indeed, they will be instruments to interact and create a dialogue with different communities. It is a way to obtain unique feedback and new information. Followers not only use messages, but publish images and video that will enrich StoRIES' communication. Similarly, social media are great platforms where users can debate about the project, its objective, and the results.

CLERENS will manage all the social media accounts, guaranteeing consistency in the communication and avoiding overlapping. Also, the two social media platforms selected complements each other, – e.g., the user groups differ and the way the messages will be conveyed is different as well. The social media platform that will be used are:

- Twitter (@StoRIES_H2020), a social media and news platform. It is often used for “live tweeting”, e.g., communicating through the platform in a short manner (280 characters maximum) during a specific event. It is an efficient tool to make an activity accessible not only to the people who are physically there, but also to those who can only follow it online. Similarly, by posting pictures and comments, everyone can easily engage with other actors. Through live tweeting, and smart use of hashtags, users receive information, and the event gains visibility. It is also a great instrument to comprehend, at the end of the activity, what kind of demographic was involved in each event. As suggested by the European Commission's guidelines, the handles @EU_H2020 and @cinea_eu, and the hashtags #H2020 and #CINEA_EU will be used in StoRIES' tweets, to maximise their visibility. A playful, concise and enthusiastic style of writing will be adopted, using emoticons to engage the audience. Partners will have visibility by being tagged on either the text of the tweet or in pictures. CLERENS has created and will operate an account on this platform.

Figure 4: Social media post on Twitter

- LinkedIn (StoRIES Project), an online service created for professional networking and discussion on topics related to businesses and professional activities. The website allows the consortium partners and other stakeholders to engage in a space specifically designed for professional interactions. The StoRIES company page will be used to inform LinkedIn users about the project. Hopefully, this will lead to a stronger relationship between the parties, and the development of new connections between the several interested actors. The style of writing in this platform is significantly different compared to the one for Twitter, since it has no character limit and allows more intricate phrasing. CLERENS has created and will operate an account on this platform under the name "StoRIES Project".

Figure 5: Social media post on LinkedIn

- Facebook (Stories Project H2020) is an online social network that allows its users to connect with friends, share similar interests, exchange messages, create and join groups, and use a variety of applications. It can be used for personal purposes, as well as professional. This platform gives a way to communicate directly with the large public, specifically the ones interested in the project as well as a collecting their insight through interaction. The project intends to use this platform to raise awareness by sharing regular updates about the project.

Figure 6: Social media post of Facebook

- YouTube (StoRIES Project) is a social media platform on which its users can share videos. The project will make use of this platform as a means to showcase the research infrastructures available in the framework of the project. In addition, it will host the project videos, which will explain the vision and objectives of the project.

Figure 7: StoRIES YouTube channel

2.2.3 Analysis of social media data

CLERENS will investigate the social media activities related to the project. As hashtags are extensively used on social networks, they will be used to comprehend the motivations that drive the users who

are commenting on StoRIES. By monitoring the messages, it will be possible to understand the quality of the communication activities prepared, how different audiences interact with the published content, and ways to improve and adjust the communication strategy. This will also be a good method to do geographical analysis, identify key figures, and which stakeholder group take part in the discussion.

For the social media channels, the built-in analytics tool will provide information on the followers' growth, the engagement rate and the conversations around the project and the topics. This information will provide data on the awareness of the audience on the project.

As with the website, CLERENS will rely on Google Analytics to measure the impact of StoRIES communication efforts.

2.2.4 Newsletter

A bi-annual newsletter will be created in order to provide to relevant audience up-to-date information about StoRIES. The newsletter will be sent to StoRIES partners firstly for internal review, and then to relevant stakeholders beyond the project community. Each relevant stakeholder will be able to subscribe to the newsletter via a form online, shared on social media to enable a wider dissemination of the newsletter. A subscription form will be included on the project website, structured according to the instructions from relevant WPs. The partners of StoRIES will promote the newsletter publication through their own communication channels and providing content, when requested.

The newsletter will be structured as follows: Overview of the progress of the project – Announcement of milestones – News articles published on the website – Deliverables and reports – Press review (news related to the topic).

The first issue has been sent out in M9 (Appendix H).

2.2.5 Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)

CLERENS will aim to ensure the optimization of StoRIES website in order to have better visibility in the different search engines. To achieve that:

- A) The website needs to be easily screened and indexed by search engines;
- B) Content needs to be easy-to-share.

This way, the website will be highly ranked by the search engines, being able to effectively reach StoRIES' targets.

2.3 Leaflets, posters and roll-up

A promotional project leaflet for the large non-specialist community as well as the community of relevant stakeholders (i.e., to be also used for dissemination purposes) will be developed and will be distributed to partners' organisations (to be further spread throughout their networks and channels) and on public events. A general project poster along with a roll-up has also been developed in order to be used for events and exhibitions. Three different products will be delivered in the course of the project.

1. Design and printout of a general project leaflets (M6) with printing to be decided according to necessity

2. Design and printout of a general project poster (M6) with printing to be decided according to necessity

3. Design and printout of a roll-up for use at events and exhibitions (M6) with printing to be decided according to necessity.

For all materials, the visual identity guidelines will be respected. All in all, this set of communication tools will be able to reach a large community, with relatively little costs.

2.4 Promotional video

StoRIES will create a presentation video. The video will include the vision and the objectives of the project. Thanks to the inputs from the coordinator and other partners, the video will be outsourced to an external provider. The video is meant to be projected in multiple ways at events, workshops, conferences, policy conferences and through social media. Its effectiveness to engage audiences and its promotion strategy will be documented in future communication reports.

2.5 Media relations

The opportunity to present the project on generalist and/or specialised media, such as local or national press, magazines, radio or TV programmes, will be sought. General media will play a key role in reaching the public and informing it about the project; specialist media will be used to reach specific stakeholder groups based on their potential or desired role in StoRIES replication activities. Both of them help raise the relevance of the project.

Press material related to StoRIES, articles in national and international magazines and papers and other publications (e.g., International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems, Journal of Power Engineering, Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks Journal, Journal of Power Sources, etc.), will be published on the StoRIES website. They will also be further promoted using social media and the newsletter.

CLERENS will coordinate the media strategy. Stakeholder associations which have a strong communication team will have a very important role in disseminating the press releases or involving media. A press release will be prepared and launched in the following important milestones of StoRIES such as: project kick-off; lab and demo results publication, high-level EU events and conferences in Brussels.

Appendix D presents the foreseen press releases and press conferences.

2.6 StoRIES related events

As the next sections will explain, the consortium will participate and co-organise scientific and industrial events, including special workshops, tutorials or industry days, aimed at presenting the StoRIES results. StoRIES Consortium partners will also participate at external events for dissemination purposes.

Appendix E presents a to-be-filled list of events which StoRIES members will attend.

2.6.1 Awareness raising events

Participation and feedback from stakeholders are key elements of this master plan. Most of the previously mentioned channels— website, newsletter, social media, and leaflets – will be used to contact the parties and inform them about the event.

A continuous evaluation of impact and planning of exploitation activities will be conducted to maximise the dissemination of results and to express them in terms that are readily understandable to stakeholders in industry, suppliers and authorities in order to accelerate the implementation of the research findings. This will be done also to promote the dissemination of the project findings through presentations at webinars, technical conferences and other events.

To provide an overview of what will be organised, the following sections provide a classification of the events.

2.6.1.1 Webinars

The Consortium will organise webinars for dissemination purposes. Specific events (physical or online) describing the role of research in the development of the StoRIES project will be organised.

Webinars are great communication tools, as they allow interactions in real time and sharing of documents easily. There is also the possibility to record webinars, further increasing the possibilities for the audience to obtain sound information about the project. The language of the webinars will be English, and participation will be promoted using the previously mentioned channels (e.g. social media, newsletter, and website).

As it will be explained in the following chapter, partners can organise webinars for dissemination purposes. However, they are invited to contact CLERENS in advance to better coordinate their action.

2.6.1.2 Final event

CLERENS will organise the final StoRIES' event to present project results to EU Policy makers, in Brussels, as well as to the industry stakeholders, research community and the wider public. Many key stakeholders will have the possibility to discuss the results achieved by the project, discuss the challenges and solutions encountered in the four years, and debate the legacy of the project.

2.6.2 Participation to external events

The dissemination of StoRIES activities through presentation at external events, such as conferences and exhibitions, will play a significant role in the project. CLERENS, together with other partners, will prepare and update a list of events (either their own or other StoRIES stakeholders' events). It will be a shared responsibility of the consortium's participants to speak at these events on behalf of the StoRIES project. CLERENS will also prepare the basic set of slides and update them regularly. Predictably, external events are a great way to engage previously unreached stakeholders, or to provide specific information, adapting the content and language to the audience.

The consortium of StoRIES project will draw on a solid network that will allow dissemination of the project results to a wide range of stakeholders. StoRIES project will aim to ensure that the spectrum of potentially interested actors will be extensively covered. Furthermore, external events will allow for cooperation with similar projects and initiatives by sharing lessons learnt.

3 INTERNAL COORDINATION, COMMUNICATION AND PROCEDURES

As said before, CLERENS is the leader regarding the communication and dissemination. Still, other consortium partners will also provide significant contributions to the outreach activities. CLERENS will take care of content production, coordination and adaptation, as it will be explained in the following sections.

3.1 Content production and delivery

As just said, during the project, several partners will prepare communication materials. However, before being published, the material will be analysed by CLERENS. The coordination and intervention from CLERENS will happen as follow:

A) For content produced by a partner

The coordination procedure is the following

1. The partners send its communication material to CLERENS.
2. CLERENS assesses whether it overlaps with other communication initiatives from the consortium and whether it is coherent with StoRIES strategy.
3. If CLERENS believes it is suitable, the partner has the "green light" to publish the materials.

The partner can publish the content both through the StoRIES channels and through its own ones. The partner shall provide the other members of the consortium a fair amount of exposure.

B) For contents produced by an external source

The communication material produced by actors external to the consortium may be taken into account and used. However, the partner must first:

1. Identify and classify the external content
2. Assess and conclude whether the content contributes to StoRIES' communication and dissemination objectives.

If partners identify material which may be useful to StoRIES, they are invited to contact CLERENS to avoid overlapping, similarly to point A.

C) Interactions with media

CLERENS is the main actor in establishing and maintaining relationships with media. However, if partners have the opportunity to interact with media. CLERENS will be available to support with any procedure, material or advice to partners.

3.2 Translation

As stated in the previous section, all the communication material shall be in English.

However, in order to foster and ensure a better dissemination strategy for the project, some communication material can also be made available in other languages in case this is needed.

3.3 Dissemination procedures

Every dissemination activity must be approved by the consortium, as described in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

3.3.1 Tracking and reporting of dissemination activities

As stated by Article 29.1 of the GA, each partner must effectively disseminate its results, taking into account the confidentiality agreements set in the GA and CA:

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

Besides, according to article 29.1 of the GA, any Partner that intends to disseminate its results must give a notice at least 45 days in advance.

“A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.”

Any other partner of the consortium may object within 30 days of receiving notification, as stated by article 29.1.

“Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed.”

3.4 Internal communication and repository

All partners will be regularly informed about the project status, planning, and any other relevant issue in order to obtain maximum transparency and awareness. All the documents shall be transmitted or made available on the private internal repository on SharePoint. In addition, direct transmission of information to the partners will be used where appropriate.

Conference calls between WP leaders, task leaders and the project coordinator will be held bi-monthly, so that it is possible to monitor the progress of project activities and to timely detect possible problems in order to mitigate them and to deliver an effective contingency plan (if needed).

Every official meeting of the project should be traceable on the private internal repository (Microsoft Teams) in a specific section. In particular, in the internal repository, a meeting section for the general meetings is created whereas for the WP meetings, a proper section is set-up in each WP folder.

Different communication tools will be used in order to facilitate the exchange of information. Among these tools, it is worth to mention the software used for conference calls and the private internal repository.

3.4.1 Software for conference calls

In addition to traditional software for conference calls that is widely used in the framework of European Projects, CLERENS will provide Microsoft Teams for the WP conference calls.

Microsoft Teams is a web-hosted service created and marketed by Microsoft. It is an online meeting tool, desktop sharing, and video conferencing software that enables users to meet with each other via the Internet in real time.

3.4.2 Private internal repository

An internal repository for the document exchange among the partners and for the files archiving was set-up by CLERENS. Microsoft Teams is accessible by web through a personalized account (user name and password). Figures to illustrate the Microsoft Teams repository are present in the Appendix C.

It is paramount to keep an updated record of the communication activities completed during the four years of the project. An online private repository will have a specific section dedicated to all the past communication activities undertaken by the partners. A table contemplating dissemination activities (events and communication activities) will be uploaded to the online repository and is to be completed by partners according to the activities they undertake (see Appendix E).

3.5 Open access

As stated in section 29.2 of the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications related to the results achieved within the project. They should be reported on a list present on the online internal repository, as shown on Appendix F.

4 PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

To determine the extent of the success of communication and dissemination activities, a set of indicators have been selected. The project will be monitored throughout its 4 years, and so will the online press and media coverage.

Quantitative data is collected through investigations where specific KPIs are used to rate performance. Besides, as explained before, part of the communication activities will be monitored with Google Analytics, which allows having in-depth information.

Overall, the project will be constantly monitored: the results of this investigation will be regularly communicated at the Consortium management meeting. This way, shortcomings or overlapping actions can be individuated and addressed, increasing the quality of the project’s communication and dissemination activities.

4.1 Key Performance Indicators

Table 4 presents the Key Performance Indicators used for StoRIES Communication and Dissemination tasks.

Tool	Indicators	Cut-off values
Website	1) Visits 2) Material downloads	1) <5000 = poor; 5000-10,000 = good; >10,000 = excellent 2) <50 = poor; 50-100 = good; >100 = excellent
Newsletter	1) Number of subscriptions 2) Number of clicks on newsletter	1) <80 subscriptions = poor; 80-150 = good; >150 = excellent 2) <3 = poor; 3-4 = good; >4 = excellent
Twitter	1) Followers 2) Impression for top 3 tweets	1) <100 = poor; 100-300 = good; >300 = excellent 2) <1000=poor; 1000-1500=good; >1500=excellent
LinkedIn	1) Followers 2) Engagement rate per post 3) Likes /reactions per post 4) Shares per post	1) <100 = poor; 100-300 = good; >300 = excellent 2) <6% = poor; 6-10% = good; >10% = excellent 3) <4=poor; 4-8=good; >8=excellent 4)<3=poor; 3-6=good; >6=excellent
Facebook	1) Followers 2) Likes /reactions per post	1) <50 = poor; 50-150 = good; >150 = excellent 2) <4=poor; 4-8=good; >8=excellent
Leaflets	Leaflet distribution	<500 copies = poor; 500-1,000 copies = good; >1,000 copies = excellent
Webinars	Number of conference presentations	<3 = poor, 3-7 = good, >7+ = excellent
Video	1) Views across all platform	1) <200 = poor; 200-500 = good; >500 = excellent

	2) Like/dislike ratio (if present)	2) < 4 likes/1 dislike=poor; 4 likes/1 dislike=good; 9 likes/1 dislike=Excellent
Final Event	1) Number of participants 2) Surveys	1) <60 = poor; 60-100 = good; >100 = excellent 2) Qualitative evaluation based on replies
Scientific Publications	Number of papers submitted	<3 = poor, 3-5 = good, >5 = excellent

4.2 Key positions and communications teams

Communication Manager:

Association/organisation	Main communication responsible	Support
CLERENS	Adeola Adeoti	Emin Aliyev Lucia Sardone Valentina Ferrara Patrick Clerens

4.3 Roles and responsibilities of partners

The communication strategy foresees the active involvement of all project partners. CLERENS is the WP5 leader and is responsible for the communication activities by ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and support the full communication of the project’s content and results. EERA will contribute to the expansion of the dissemination of results achieved by the StoRIES project by reaching out to the energy and climate research community. EASE, as a member-based umbrella association covering the largest communities in the energy storage sector from SMEs, TSOs, DSOs, technology providers, energy companies as well as research centres, will provide complementary outreach and ensure further enhancement of the overall project’s visibility and impact. All partners are strongly committed to promoting project outcomes and involve stakeholders in project participatory approach. They will help prepare communication pieces, participate in and help organise events, provide information, feedback and inputs on dissemination activities. The universities and RTOs are of great importance for providing scientific publications whilst the commercial partners are focused on the exploitation and dissemination part of the project communication.

The cost for communication materials and equipment is all allocated in CLERENS budget for the whole project. This includes the printing of materials, website and video delivery and final event management, etc. The partners are allocated with some budget to attend relevant events to promote the project and disseminate the results.

4.4 Support Roadmap of StoRIES

Deliverable 5.2 supports the StoRIES Project in the definition of dissemination actions and communication and in line with LC-GD-9-1-2020 “Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and Innovation in support of the European Green Deal” that falls under the H2020 programme. StoRIES project contributes to providing Users a world-class research infrastructure (RI) network to foster innovation for the development of new materials for devices and hybrid storage applications. Dissemination and communication actions supports StoRIES project in order to increase its impact through key outputs. Therefore, relevant dissemination actions will target StoRIES

stakeholder groups which contain representatives of companies, European or national associations and platforms in the field of storage systems. As mentioned in the document, an important point of StoRIES is to interact with other relevant EU-funded projects in storage applications to maximize the impact of the project.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This document (D5.2) provides guidance for where and how to apply content, tools and resource indicators. It explains contexts, defines roles and assigns responsibilities. The document presents the project profile handbook, which is an integral part of the visual aspects of the communication efforts, including the communication channels and target audience (participants, stakeholders, media, public officials etc.) that were of particular interest to the project. Furthermore, it touched upon measures to take in order to achieve the biggest impact. This includes descriptions of what roles partners will be serving, and how this also may influence how time and other resources best should be applied for maximum results. The deliverable serves as strategy document, but some of its content will be dynamic by nature. KPIs will have to be updated as the project learns more about the different domains and changes in policies. The document also touches upon how to join forces with other ES related platforms and projects to increase the impact of StoRIES and its exploitation activities. Analysing the KPIs and overall actions in this context, it is described that StoRIES is currently following planned goals.

The road ahead: The coming year will introduce several events that will be newsworthy. The project will bring more results to be disseminated, some relevant deliverables will be published. All these results will demand updated dissemination material, will generate more feedback from the public, stakeholders and integrators. In addition, the access to the infrastructure (TNA) will be promoted through specific communication channels and call for proposals. The project will therefore have to consider best practice for streamlining support questions and request for material. StoRIES may have to consider contingency plans if unexpected situations should arise. There may also be other events that will demand for actions to be taken. Final version of Deliverable 5.2 will include relevant sections and will be based on lessons learned during the next stage of the project.

Appendixes

Appendix A – Templates

Appendix A presents images related to all the templates elaborated for the StoRIES project.

Figure 8 Presentation template

Figure 9 Presentation template

Figure 10 Text template

Figure 11 Deliverable template

© E.# - "Deliverable title"
CO/CI/PU

D#.# - "Deliverables title"

Work Package Number - Work Package Name
Task Number - Task Name
Due date of deliverable: Day Month Year
Actual submission date: Day Month Year

Project Acronym	StoRIES
Call	H2020-1C-GD-2020
Grant Agreement No.	101036910
Project Start Date	01-11-2021
Project End Date	31-10-2025
Duration	48 months

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101036910

2

Figure 12 Deliverable template

Name of Meeting
Location, DD Month 202_

MINUTES OF MEETING
NAME OF MEETING
 Location, Date

ATTENDANCE LIST

Day 1

Classification	Name	Signature

- Text
- Text

Decision:

- Text
- Text
- Text

Decision:

- Text
- Text
- Text

Decision:

Table 1: Example of Table

Title	Title	Title	Title

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1

Figure 13 Minutes of the meeting template

Appendix B – Project logo, EU logo and appropriate text

Figure 14 StoRIES logo

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Figure 15 EU logo and acknowledgment

Appendix C – Website, repository and communication material

Appendix C presents images related to the website and the repository platform.

Website

Homepage

Figure 16 StoRIES website homepage

Example of other pages

Figure 17 StoRIES website homepage "Latest news"

Figure 18 Internal structure of the repository based on Sharepoint

Appendix D – Press releases and dissemination material list

Appendix D presents the foreseen dissemination materials.

Table 4 Dissemination material list

Material	Event	Channels of publication and country	Date
Video	N/A	YouTube Belgium	N/A
Poster	N/A	Not released yet	N/A
Leaflet	N/A	Not released yet	N/A
Roll up	N/A	Not released yet	N/A

Appendix E – Events list

Appendix E presents a list of external events where the consortium’s members have participated or will participate and a list of the event organised by members of the consortium.

Table 5 Participation in external events

Event	Date	Location	Activities performed	Partners involved	People reached
SUPEERA workshop focused on Energy Storage and Fuel Cells and Hydrogen technologies/sectors	10 May 2022	Padua, Italy	Presentation of Project	KIT	Industrial and scientific community
4 th Project Meeting POLY STORAGE	18-20 May 2022	Helsinki, Finland	Advertisement for TNA call	KIT	Academia, industry, research

					institution, early-stage researchers
International Conference of Young Scientists on Energy and Natural Sciences Issues (CYSENI)	24 May 2022	Online	Presentation of project with focus on the early-stage researchers	KIT	Academia, early-stage researchers, EU13 representatives
First Clean Energy Working Group meeting	8 June 2022	Online	Presentation of project	KIT	Academia, EC, Industry
PANTERA Workshop "The EIRIE platform enabling R&I activities and investment in smart grids" at MELECON 2022	14 June 2022	Palermo, Italy	Round Table discussion	KIT	Academia, Research
EERA JP Smart Grids General Assembly	14 June 2022	Palermo, Italy	Presentation of project	KIT	Academia, Research
The First Symposium for YouNg Chemists: Innovation and Sustainability (SYNC2022),	20-23 June 2022	Rome, Italy	Presentation of project	KIT	Academia
EERA Annual Strategy Meeting 2022	22-23 June 2022	Prague, Czech Republic	Presentation of project	EERA/KIT	Academia
Workshop on energy storage and its crucial role in the energy transition with focus on hybrid solution	23 June 2022	Messina, Italy	Presentation of project	CNR	Industrial and scientific community
EASE Event - Energy Security Needs Energy Storage	30 June 2022	Brussels, Belgium	Networking	KIT	Industrial and scientific community
Power Our Future Conference	5-8 July 2022	Vitoria, Spain	Presentation of project	KIT	Industrial and scientific community

Table 6 Events organised by the Consortium

Event	Date	Location	Activities performed	Partners involved	People reached
Kick-off Meeting	25 Nov 2021	Ulm, Germany	Presentation of project's activities	Consortium	Consortium
Second Project Meeting	11 May 2022	Padua, Italy	Presentation of project's activities	Consortium	Consortium
TNA Call Launch	11 May 2022	Padua, Italy	Presentation on 1st TNA Call	Consortium	Industrial and scientific community

Appendix F – Scientific articles and publications list

Table 7 List of scientific articles and publication list

Article/Publication	Journal	Partners involved
Hybrid Energy Storage and Hydrogen Supply Based on Aluminum—a Multiservice Case for Electric Mobility and Energy Storage Services	Advanced Material Technologies - Germany	KIT, UNIPG
Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition	BMC - Springer Nature - Germany	KIT
Aluminum Steam Oxidation in the Framework of Long-Term Energy Storage: Experimental Analysis of the Reaction Parameters Effect on Metal Conversion Rate	Energy Technology - Germany	KIT, UNIPG

Appendix G – List of Public Deliverables

Table 8 List of public deliverables

Deliverable no and WP	Lead Participant	Type	Title
D2.1/WP2	KIT	R	Validation of the Selection Panel
D2.2/WP2	ECCSEL	R	General rules for TA according to Access Policy
D2.3/WP2	ECCSEL	R	Access Policy: Agreement between coordinator, infrastructure owner and user

D3.7/WP3	KIT	R	Education Program rules and procedures
D5.1/WP5	CLERENS	R	Report on project identity and website

Appendix H – Newsletter

Figure 19 First Newsletter issue

Updates from the Project

StoRIES Newsletter // 1st issue

Introduction from the Project Coordination Team

The recent geopolitical developments show that Europe must become independent in terms of energy supply, which can only be achieved through intensive use of **renewable energies** and flexibilisation through the use of **energy storage** options. The highly efficient and effective solutions needed for, e.g., the establishment of seasonal/annual energy storage offering volumetric energy densities close to those of fossil fuels (2-10 kWh L⁻¹), however, require strong integration of industrial and academic efforts.

StoRIES project fosters a **European ecosystem** of industry and research organisations in the variegated field of energy storage, aiming at the development of novel concepts and technologies to achieve more **performing, competitive and cost-effective** energy storage systems. It focuses on cross-cutting solutions to accelerate innovation across the entire value chain by taking an interdisciplinary and multi-level approach.

Funded under EU Horizon 2020 programme, StoRIES is led by Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and includes **17 full partners** and more than **30 beneficiaries** from 17 countries. Altogether, it provides access to **64 world-class facilities**, including a European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures landmark, technology institutes, universities, and industries.

StoRIES establishes an ecosystem to foster open science and promote new energy technology standards. Users have access to the most advanced research infrastructures to research on improving materials for devices and optimizing hybrid energy systems. In addition, StoRIES creates a **Materials Acceleration Platform (MAP)** to offer information exchange, demonstration, support services and on-the-tool training. StoRIES also focuses on analysing socio-technical and environmental aspects of new developments. Additionally, young scientists receive targeted **training** at top international research facilities and workshops, working in a coordinated team to accelerate the storage technology innovation chain. Two documents-**Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** and the **Roadmap** for hybridisation of energy storage will chart the European path for Energy Storage in terms of technological, sustainable and also legal aspects to achieve a full EU energy independence.

By promoting complementary expertise, interdisciplinary cooperation and a broader exchange of knowledge and technologies throughout the academic world and with industry, StoRIES will significantly facilitate innovation and the development of improved energy storage solutions.

The first Transnational Access Call: StoRIES project has launched its first Transnational Access (TNA) call for research and innovation projects for the year 2022, under the call topic "Application oriented hybrid and sustainable energy storage solutions". [Read more](#)

Working Groups: The governance of the Working Groups (WG1 to WG4) has been fully defined. Furthermore, the StoRIES **WG1** activities started with an online workshop that took place on 3 June 2022 to collect the experts' feedback on the first structure of the roadmap, as well as the definition and terminology of hybridization for energy storage. In addition, within **WG2**, the workshop on call topic definition on 18 February 2022 focused on agreeing on the topic(s) for the first TNA call for the StoRIES project. Although held online the use of interactive tools allowed for an open brainstorming session. The call topic was held quite open to maximise the audience which would feel addressed by the topics. The brainstorming session also showed that there possibly is a large variety of ideas for submissions for the discussed topics. As a result, the summarising title "Application oriented hybrid and sustainable energy storage solutions" was defined. [Read more](#)

News

The StoRIES Working Group 4 kick-off meeting took place with an online event on 22 June 2022 to launch the beginning of the activity and collaboration.

[Read more](#)

The first StoRIES Transnational Access (TNA) call for applications for research and innovation projects is now open!

[Read more](#)

The second StoRIES project meeting was held on 11 May 2022 in Padua (Italy) and gathered more than 60 participants (in-person and online) from 11 European countries.

[Read more](#)

The "Storage Research Infrastructure Eco-System" (StoRIES) project officially kicked off with a hybrid meeting on 25 November 2021 in Ulm (Germany).

[Read more](#)

Deliverables and Reports

- D2.1 [Validation of the Selection Panel](#)
- D2.2 [General rules for TA according to Access Policy](#)
- D2.3 [Access Policy: Agreement between coordinator, infrastructure owner and user](#)
- D3.7 [Education Program rules and procedures](#)
- D5.1 [Report on project identity and website](#)

Articles

- [Hybrid Energy Storage and Hydrogen Supply Based on Aluminum—a Multiservice Case for Electric Mobility and Energy Storage Services \(2022\)](#)
- [Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition \(2022\)](#)

Share this newsletter with colleagues!

[Project website](#)

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